

Attach a price to an item that is broadcast on the station

This can be done through the creation of a contract for every predefined track, podcast, streaming and program. You can set:

- the amount of the revenue
- the currency
- the beginning date of the contract
- the expiration date of the contract

RC

Settings

Log out

English

Logged in

Hello, RC !

- [Radio Dashboard](#)
- [Telephony Records](#)
- [Configure Station](#)
- [Manage Content](#)
- [Manage Users](#)
- [Finance](#)

New button. If the user manages just 1 station, it should bring directly to slide 4. If he/she manages more stations the button brings to slide 3, where he/she can choose the station

Add a Finance section on Rootio

RC Settings Log out English ▼

[RADIO](#) [Status](#) [Stations](#) [Programs](#) [Music Programs](#) [Schedule](#)

Finance - select station

Show entries Search:

Name (frequency) ▼	Summary	Previous Program	Current Program	Next Program	Finance
Test FM (93.7)	5 successful, 9 failed, 44172 Scheduled	Damian-test-music program at 2020-03-02 16:00:00+00:00	None	Random Music Patongo at 2020-03-26 00:00:00+00:00	Finance
Patongo Community Radio (103.8)	0 successful, 0 failed, 44172 Scheduled	Random Music Patongo at 2020-03-25 12:00:00+00:00	Random Music Patongo at 2020-03-25 18:00:00+00:00	Random Music Patongo at 2020-03-26 00:00:00+00:00	Finance
Bukwo FM (105.6)	0 successful, 0 failed, 44172 Scheduled	None	None	None	Finance

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries Previous 1 Next

Go to slide 4

FINANCE

- Paid content: new contract for a single item (track, podcast, streaming)
- Paid content: new contract for entire programs
- List of paid contents
- Add an expense/bill
- Add a source of revenue
- Set our annual financial target
- Financial report

Slide 5

Slide 6

Slide 9

Slide 10

Slide 12

Slide 14

Slide 15

New Contract

Content source

Track
Stream
Podcast

List of the items

Here there is a list of the items contained in the selected "content source" (the tracks / streams / podcasts belonging to the station)

Start of the contract

End of the contract

The station will collect money from this track

Purchaser

Amount

Currency

[Go to the list of paid contents](#)

through this button you'll go to slide n. 9

Save

Attach a Price to an entire program

Program Name

Here there is a list of the station's programs

ATTENTION: this program already contain profitable items:

Value:

When the program contain item with a set amount of revenue, the system will show automatically the amount.

[Go to the list of paid contents](#)

Assign a revenue to the program

The station will collect money from this program

Currency

DISCLAIMER: the system will count only the amount set here and not those previously set on tracks, streamings, podcasts

Start of the contract

Purchaser

End of the contract

Amount

[Save](#)

If no revenue have been set for the single items, you can attach a price to an entire program.

Content Dashboard

(also for podcast, streaming, program)

Tracks

[Add +](#)[Go to programs](#)Network: Show entriesSearch:

Name	Networks	Description	Profitable	Content Type			
weather forecast	Testy network	play the most recent weather forecast		Media	0 Files	Edit	Delete
Victor Sullivan MarkBere Wed11 Interview	Testy network	An interview with Victor Sullivan about his new book Who was Johnny Wheels	✓ 5 €	Media	1 Files	Edit	Delete

A new column shows if the station will collect money from the item and the amount

Test FM Schedule

Timezone: Europe/Lisbon

Music-Program ■ Cloud-Program ■ Success ■ Failure ■ No Media ■

Add Programs

+ Add Recurring

Filter...

Damians Test Programme

Damians extra extra program

Damians Test Music Programme

Damians test with ads

List of paid contents

Slide 15

[Go to the report](#)

Show entries

Search:

Purchaser	Amount	Type	date of broadcast	End of the contract	Played	Edit	
Butcher	3€	Track	16/03/2020 15:30	31/12/2020	Yes	Edit	Delete
Restaurant X	10€	Program	18/03/2020 17:30	30/06/2020	No (lost 10€)	Edit	Delete
						Edit	Delete

to the track?

Add an expense/bill

Show entries

Search:

Provider	Amount	Type	Date	Frequency	Ending	Edit	
Mr. Blue	250€	Rent	01/02/2020	Monthly	31/12/2020	Edit	Delete
X shop	40€	Microphone	16/02/2020	one time	16/02/2020	Edit	Delete
						Edit	Delete

Add (edit) an expense/bill

Provider

Amount

Select the expense

Rent, electricity, insurance,
license...

Describe the expense (if you selected "other")

single payment

Date

payment every

Date

Ending

SAVE

Add a source of revenue

Show entries

Search:

Slide 9

[Go to the list of paid contents](#)

Slide 13

[Add +](#)

Slide 15

[Go to the report](#)

Name	Amount	Description	Date	Frequency	Ending	Edit	Slide 13
Mrs Green	50€	Donation	01/01/2020	one time	01/01/2020	Edit	Delete
Municipality	100€	Sponsorship	01/01/2020	Monthly	31/12/2020	Edit	Delete
						Edit	Delete

Add a source of revenue

Provider

Amount

Select a source

Donation, sponsorship,
member fee...

Describe the source (if you selected "other")

single earning

Date

earning every

Date

Ending

SAVE

Annual Financial target

The amount of money the radio needs to collect in order to be sustainable

Year

Currency

consider all the already set expenses of the year

add another amount

The target of the station for this year is:

3.000 €

Financial report

The financial target

Tot. Income	
Tot. Expenses	

Download a CSV

Type of report

Period

Filter

Currency

Date	Amount	Description
02/03/2020	+2 €	Track adv. O'fas
05/03/2020	+4 €	Program Town Hall
06/03/2020	-25€	Electricity bill

Paid contents, donation, sponsorships...

Complete report
Revenues report
Expenses Report
Potential loss from contents not broadcasted
...